

A Study on Optimum Portfolio Using Abnormal Return With Special Reference to Nifty

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Seema Balan

*Scholar, Department of Management Studies
Sri Chandrasekharendra Saraswati ViswaMahavidyalaya, Enathur,
Kanchipuram, Tamil Nadu*

Dr. B. Balaji Srinivasan

*Associate Professor, Department of Management Studies
Sri Chandrasekharendra Saraswati Viswa Mahavidyalaya, Enathur, Kanchipuram,
Tamil Nadu*

Abstract

The Indian stock market had witnessed an incredible growth in the last two years. Almost all the stocks in the nifty extremely outperformed and so is the nifty. Even the recent economic reforms like demonetisation have little impact on the stock market. Investors who were waited with patience all these times got fructified from their investments. The study had taken into consideration the 48 stocks in Nifty50 for two years from April 2015 to March 2017. This study was made an attempt to construct an optimum portfolio using the concepts of abnormal return based on CAPM. The portfolio with all scrips having positive return and the beta value almost near to market beta performs better than other portfolios.

Keywords: Nifty, CAPM, beta, abnormal return, optimum portfolio

JEL Classification Codes: G10, G11, G12

Introduction

Out of the different investment avenues, security market is one of the risky one. All investors want to earn more return from their investment. They always prefer for happy situations and want to stay away from the unfavourable ones. The affection to be happy always has given birth to the term risk. In order to reduce the risk the investor has to select the strong share in terms of profitability. The hope of the investors regarding the future cash flows is reflected on the share prices. Investment in equity has the advantage of liquidity as well as profitability. In general equity investment attracts dividend and capital appreciation as a result of higher market price.

Equities are highly risky investments due to certain market conditions. The risk can be reduced if we construct a portfolio using the shares considering their beta. Beta indicates the volatility of the scrip with relation to the market. A beta above 1 indicates the scrip is more volatile than the market.

The **NIFTY 50** index is National Stock Exchange of India’s benchmark stock market index for Indian equity market, launched on 21st April 1996. The NIFTY 50 covers 12 sectors (as on Oct 7, 2017) of the Indian economy and offers investment managers exposure to the Indian market in one portfolio. There are nearly 2000 companies listed in NSE and the total turnover in the cash market is Rs. 50, 55,913 crores as on 31st March 2017.

Capital Asset Pricing Model

The capital asset pricing model was the work of financial economist (and, later, Nobel laureate in economics) William Sharpe, set out in his 1970 book “Portfolio Theory and Capital Markets.” CAPM model is used to determine an appropriate rate of return of an asset so that it can be included in the portfolio.

Markowitz modern portfolio theory deals about unsystematic risk reduction through diversification. Diversification still does not solve the systematic risk associated with the investment. Even any portfolio with all the shares in the market cannot eliminate the risk. So while calculating the deserved return, the investor’s biggest challenge is systematic risk. Thus CAPM evolved as a way to measure the systematic risk.

The graph below depicts the SML. SML refers to security market line and the slope of it is the market risk premium and it intercepts the y-axis at risk free rate. In market equilibrium the expected return is equal to required rate of return

Figure 1.1 Pictorial representation of CAPM

Beta

Beta is a measure used in fundamental analysis to decide the volatility of an asset or portfolio in relation to the overall market. It is represented as “ β ” (beta).

$$\text{Beta} = \frac{\text{Covariance (Market, Stock)}}{\text{Variance (Market)}}$$

If beta is equal to 1, then the scrip is moving along with the benchmark index. If beta is greater than 1, the scrip is more volatile and if beta less than 1, the scrip is less volatile than the index.

Abnormal return

Abnormal return is the financial performance by a single stock or portfolio of stocks that varies from the market average. An abnormal return can be positive or negative, depending on whether the stock outperformed or underperformed the average market performance.

Abnormal return = performance of individual stock or portfolio – index performance

Optimum Portfolio

Optimal portfolio is a portfolio that gives maximum return at a given level of risk. Optimum portfolio comes under Markowitz theory states that the investors will act rationally, always making decision aimed at maximising their returns for their acceptable level of risk. It is a portfolio that maximises an investor's preference with respect to return and risk.

Literature Review

Niklas et.al (2017) stated spatial auto regressive model for cross sectional correlation of abnormal returns and identified that abnormal returns of firms in the same industry are correlated, where as abnormal returns of the firms in different industries are not correlated.

(Kadan, 2014) downside risk, rare disasters, as well as other risk attributes. We offer two different approaches. First is an equilibrium framework generalizing the Capital Asset Pricing Model, two- fund separation, and the security market line. Second is an axiomatic approach resulting in a systematic risk measure as the unique solution to a risk allocation problem. Both approaches lead to similar results extending the traditional beta to capture multiple dimensions of risk. The results lend themselves naturally to empirical investigation. (JEL D81, G11, G12 generalised systematic risk. They used two different approaches to generalise the systematic risk. The equilibrium model, CAPM and the axiomatic approach which looked into the risk allocation problem were the two approaches used by him in his study. The result of the study showed that a variety of risk attributes was explained by beta.

Gabih et.al (2006) used Black-Scholes model of a complete financial market consisting of one risky stock and a risk free bond and demonstrated how a portfolio manager optimally over- or underperforms a benchmark under different economic conditions depending on its attitude towards risk and choice of the benchmark

Fama & French (2004) discussed the logic of CAPM focusing on its predictions about risk and expected return. They concluded that the empirical model suggested by Sharpe and Linter has never been an empirical success. Unfortunately, the empirical record of the model is poor; to invalidate the way it is used in applications. The CAPM practical problems may be a sign of theoretical failings, the result of many simplifying assumptions. But they may also be caused by difficulties in implementing valid tests of the model.

Ibbotson & Jeffery (1975) used a procedure that permits changes in beta, but imposes the restriction that betas are identical across firms. In addition, it uses only a small fraction of the available data

Markowitz (1952 and 1959) is the father of modern portfolio theory. He formulated the portfolio problem as a choice of the mean and variance of a portfolio of assets. Markowitz theory is also based on diversification. He believes in asset correlation and in combining assets in a manner to lower risk.

Research Objectives

1. To find return of each scrip in the nifty index and nifty.
2. To find beta value for each company in the nifty index.
3. To construct portfolios with respect to selected scrip's on the basis of beta.
4. To find abnormal returns of the portfolio
5. To select optimum portfolio based on abnormal return.

Research Methodology

Data and Sampling Size

The study is conducted for nifty 50 index & nifty 50 shares. The adjusted weekly closing prices for 2 years of trading sessions from April 2015 to March 2017 are taken. The type of data is secondary.

Research Design

Descriptive research design is used in the study

Statistical Tools Used

Variance, covariance, regression and ADF test are the statistical tools used.

Analysis and Interpretation

Step-1

Computation of Return

Calculation of return of the scrips using the formula $R = \ln(P_{t+1} \div P_t)$,

Where, R is the return, P_{t+1} is the price of the scrip at t+1 period and P_t is the price of the scrip at time period t. ADF test is used to check the sationarity of the returns and found the returns are stationary.

Step-2

Computation of Beta

Beta measures the volatility of scrip in relation to the benchmark index

$$\text{Beta} = \text{Cov}(R_i, R_m) \div \text{Var}(R_m)$$

i.e., the covariance of market return with stock returns \div variance of market return

Table 1 Arrangement of shares on the basis of beta

Sl.No.	Scrip Name	Beta Value
1	Vedanta Ltd.	2.0004
2	Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Ltd.	1.8093
3	Hindalco Industries Ltd.	1.7363
4	ICICI Bank Ltd.	1.6548
5	State Bank of India	1.6115
6	Tata Motors Ltd.	1.5281
7	Tata Steel Ltd.	1.3966
8	India bulls Housing Finance Ltd.	1.3251
9	Larsen & Toubro Ltd.	1.2937
10	Bosch Ltd.	1.2457
11	Yes Bank Ltd.	1.2438
12	IndusInd Bank Ltd.	1.1995
13	Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Ltd.	1.1751
14	Housing Development Finance Corporation Ltd.	1.1550
15	Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	1.1488
16	Bajaj Finance Ltd.	1.1345

17	Zee Entertainment Enterprises Ltd.	1.1292
18	Axis Bank Ltd.	1.0932
19	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	1.0796
20	UPL Ltd.	1.0561
21	GAIL (India) Ltd.	1.0514
22	Aurobindo Pharma Ltd.	1.0339
23	Ambuja Cements Ltd.	1.0294
24	I T C Ltd.	1.0259
25	Oil & Natural Gas Corporation Ltd.	1.0197
26	UltraTech Cement Ltd.	1.0168
27	Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	0.9324
28	Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	0.9210
29	Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd.	0.9044
30	Reliance Industries Ltd.	0.8616
31	Eicher Motors Ltd.	0.8471
32	Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd.	0.8221
33	HDFC Bank Ltd.	0.8133
34	Tech Mahindra Ltd.	0.8119
35	Asian Paints Ltd.	0.7896
36	NTPC Ltd.	0.7547
37	Hindustan Unilever Ltd.	0.7375
38	Indian Oil Corporation Ltd.	0.7311
39	Coal India Ltd.	0.6884
40	Bharti Airtel Ltd.	0.6870
41	Cipla Ltd.	0.6784
42	Power Grid Corporation of India Ltd.	0.6725
43	Tata Consultancy Services Ltd.	0.6462
44	Bharat Petroleum Corporation Ltd.	0.6427
45	Infosys Ltd.	0.6359
46	HCL Technologies Ltd.	0.6290
47	Wipro Ltd.	0.6075
48	Lupin Ltd.	0.5602

Beta indicates the volatility of the scrip with relation to the market. A beta above 1 indicates the scrip is more volatile than the market. A beta value below 1 indicates that the scrips are less volatile than the market. From table 1, we can identify that scrip Vedanta Ltd have the highest beta of 2.004 which means the scrip is two times more volatile than nifty and so on.

Step-3 Portfolio Creation

6 portfolios of 8 scrips have been created on the basis of descending order of their beta value.

Step-4**Calculation of Expected Return Of The Portfolio**

Expected return of the portfolio has been calculated using the formula

$$ER_p = R_f + \beta_p(R_p - R_f)$$

Where,

ER_p is the expected portfolio return,

R_f is the risk free rate,

β_p is the portfolio beta,

R_p is the portfolio return

Risk free rate is the rate of treasury bills for the year 2016 and 2017

Portfolio beta describes relative volatility of individual securities in the portfolio, taken as a whole, as measured by the individual stock betas of the securities making it up.

Portfolio return is the average return of scrips in the portfolio

Step-5**Calculation of Abnormal Return**

Abnormal return is the difference between expected return of the portfolio calculated in step-4 and market return. A negative abnormal return indicates that the market performed better than each individual stock in the portfolio. From table-2 we can identify that portfolio-I and portfolio-IV are having negative abnormal returns which show the shares in portfolio performed not as much as that of the benchmark index nifty.

Table 2 Table showing abnormal return of portfolio

Sl.No.	Portfolio	Abnormal return
1	Portfolio-I	-0.17004
2	Portfolio-II	0.005616
3	Portfolio-III	0.002176
4	Portfolio-IV	0.001128
5	Portfolio-V	0.000711
6	Portfolio-VI	-0.00023

Table 3 Ranking of portfolios on the basis of abnormal return

Sl.no.	Portfolio	Abnormal return	Rank
1	Portfolio-I	-0.17004	6
2	Portfolio-II	0.005616	1
3	Portfolio-III	0.002176	2
4	Portfolio-IV	0.001128	3
5	Portfolio-V	0.000711	4
6	Portfolio-VI	-0.00023	5

Conclusion

The results show that the 2nd portfolio with shares L&T, Bosch Ltd, Yes Bank, Indusind Bank, HPCL, HDFC, Hero Motor Corporation and Bajaj Finance Ltd is having the highest

abnormal return. All these scrips show steady positive returns throughout the period. Thus we can conclude that a portfolio with shares having positive returns will give a fair return to the investor. The beta of the shares in portfolio is also near the beta of the benchmark index. While the 1st portfolio is having the least abnormal return in which almost all the shares have negative return and high betas. If the investor is ready to analyse the shares he wants to invest simply based on the returns will give him an overall picture of the scrip. Thus he can decide whether to invest in the scrip or not.

References

1. A. Gabih W. Grecksch M. Richter R. Wunderlich (2006) “optimal portfolio strategies benchmarking the stock market”, *Mathematical Methods of Operations Research*, 64(2):211-225
2. Fama and French. (2004) “The Capital Asset Pricing Model: Theory and Evidence.” *The journal of Economics Perspectives* 18(3): 25–46.
3. Kadan, Ohad. 2014. “Generalized Systematic Risk 1.” 8(May): 86–127.
4. Markowitz, H. (1952), “Portfolio Selection.” *The Journal of Finance*, 7: 77–91.
5. Niklas Ahlgren and Jan Antell (2017) “Tests for Abnormal Returns in the Presence of Event-Induced Cross-Sectional Correlation”, *Journal of Financial Econometrics*, 15(2), 286-301
6. Roger G Ibbotson & Jeffery F Jaffe (1975), “hot issue markets”, *The Journal of Finance*, 30(4): 1027–1042
7. www.nseindia.com